

THE BASICS OF SPIRITUALITY IN THE WORK OF AZHINIYAZ

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Ajiniyaz Kosybay uly (literary pseudonym Ziyuar) He was born in 1824 on the southern coast of the Aral Sea - at the mouth of the Amu Darya River in the village "Kamish Bugat" of Muynak district, where natives of the Karakalpak families Ashamaily and Kiyat lived. Azhiniyaz's father Kosybai, his brother Baltabek, and his middle brother Akjigit were brave and courageous people of their time. His mother Nazira was an eloquent, charming woman. In his youth, Ajiniyaz was gifted and diligent to study. He first studied at the madrasa of Imam Khojamurad. After his mother's death, his studies were interrupted, and he studied with his uncle Elmurad.

Along with studying in many madrassas, he was engaged in copying many books and became a notable person among the population. Already at the age of 16, he rewrote some of the works of Alisher Navoi. Further, Ajiniyaz continues his studies in Khiva. Azhiniyaz, who came to study in Khiva, initially studies at the Shergozi madrasah, where the Turkmen classical poet Makhtumkuli also studied before him. Then he graduates from the Kutlimurat Inak madrasah. Now at the entrance to the Kutlimurat-inak madrasah there is an inscription: "In this madrasah in 1840-1845 the poet Ajiniyaz Kosybai uly studied."

In the madrasah of Kutlimurat-inak, along with Islamic teachings, the legacies of Eastern classics such as Navoi, Khofiz, Saadi, Fuzuli were also studied. Ajiniyaz diligently studied the works of these great masters of poetry. Through cultural enlightenment, the poet dreamed of having a beneficial effect on the life of his oppressed people.

After graduating from the Kutlimurat-inak madrasah, he returns to his village and immediately leaves for Kazakhstan, where he lives for one year. After returning from Kazakhstan, he marries a Hamra girl from the Ashamaily clan and they have three sons and one daughter. The poet's descendants currently live in the Kungrad, Kanlikul, Shumanai districts and in the city of Nukus.

The Kungrad uprising of 1858-1859, which was one of the largest events in the history of the peoples who inhabited the Khorezm oasis, produced a great revolution in the life and poetic fate of Azhiniyaz. An educated man, an

outstanding poet, an ardent patriot Azhiniyaz could not remain indifferent to this event.

During these years, Azhiniyaz was captured by Khiva officials, as one of the leaders of the Kungrad uprising, he was exiled to Turkmenistan. While in exile, he translates many of Makhtumkuli's poems into the Karakalpak language.

Three years later, he returns to his native village, but is again persecuted and leaves for Kazakhstan.

It is assumed that this departure of Azhiniyaz to Kazakhstan is the third in a row and coincides with 1864, in which the poet Azhiniyaz arranges a poetic competition in eloquence called "Aitys" with the Kazakh poetess Kyz-Menesh. This "Aitys" has become especially popular among traditional folk competitions. It was even published in 1878 in Tashkent in the newspaper "Turkistan Ualayati".

The years of Azhiniyaz's stay in Kazakhstan coincided with the heyday of his poetic creativity. At this time, he creates a large number of his famous poems, such as "There is my people", "Is there", "Is there", "Similar", "If separated", "Farewell", etc.

After returning to his native land, he opens schools for children in the villages of "Bozatau", "Kamys Buget", "Zhetim-uzyak" and teaches children to read and write, is engaged in creativity, writes poetry.

The heartfelt feelings of a person are very deep in the poet's love lyrics. His poems "My beloved", "Beauties", "Beauties from Bozatau", "Ah, Dariha", "I have no other beloved but you", "One Peri" can deservedly be considered the crown of the love lyrics of Karakalpak classical poetry. The mastery contained in these verses has a strong influence on our modern lyric poets.

The poet's love lyrics are now turning into the most beloved songs of our modern youth. The life and work of Ajiniyaz are studied in the programs of schools and universities, and his books have been published and continue to be published in Karakalpak, Uzbek and Russian. Schools and streets are named after the poet. One of the largest and oldest universities in Karakalpakstan - the Nukus State Pedagogical Institute is named after the great poet Azhiniyaz. His poems inspire our composers and singers to create new musical works. In the years of independence, based on the libretto of the Hero of Uzbekistan, poet Ibrahim Yusupov, composer Nazhmaddin Mukhammaddinov created his musical work — the opera Azhiniyaz, which was staged at the Berdakh Musical Drama Theater.

The study of Ajiniyaz's creativity began in the 1930s. The first studies of Ajiniyaz's creativity were made by K. Ayimetov, O.Kozhurov and N. Daukaraev. The main content of N.Daukaraev's work "Essays on the history of Karakalpak literature" was devoted to the work of Azhiniyaz. In the 50s of the twentieth century, researchers K.Ayymbetov, I. Sagitov, K.Berdimuratov, S. Akhmetov, B.Ismailov and others opened new pages in the work of Azhiniyaz.

The works of Ajiniyaz in 1949,1960,1965,1975 were published in Karakalpak, in 1962 in Uzbek, in 1975 in Russian. In the 60s of the twentieth century, many unknown manuscripts of Azhiniyaz's poems were found and new studies of Azhiniyaz's creativity appeared. These are such studies as "Thoughts about the poet Azhiniyaz" by K. Bayniyazov, "Fundamentals of poetry of Azhiniyaz" by H. Hamidov, "Azhiniyaz is a master of the artistic word" by A. Karimov, "The Lover of youth" by K. Sultanov, "Some thoughts about the skill of Azhiniyaz" by A. Pirnazarov, "Literary methods and stylistic features of Azhiniyaz Kosibay uly" by A. Murtazaeva.

The comparison of Azhiniyaz's creativity with the history of the people found expression in the articles of academician S. Kamalov "Historical and ethnographic information of the people in the works of Azhiniyaz", B. Ismailov "Description of the Kungrad uprising of 1858-1859 in the works of Azhiniyaz". Azhiniyaz was not only one of the ideologists of the uprising, but also a direct participant in the "Bozatau tragedy", which was scarred as a deep wound in the history of the Karakalpaks. The severe trials that befell compatriots gave rise to the famous poem by Azhiniyaz "Bozatau":

This wonderful work depicts with deep lyricism the sadness of the motherland, the heartfelt sorrow of the people who lost their native land, were expelled from their native places. The poet poses such eternal problems as the people and the land, the citizen and the motherland.

"Bozatau" is the national sonata of the Karakalpak people, its shrine. The people say: "What kind of Karakalpak are you if you don't know "Bozatau". There is also such a funny story among the people: when during the implementation of the national demarcation of Central Asia, some chauvinists did not want to recognize the Karakalpaks as an independent people and began to express their disdain for them, then the representative of the Karakalpak people, Allayar Dosnazarov, sang the song "Bozatau". None of those present could repeat it, after which Karakalpakstan was given autonomy.

The poems of Azhiniyaz during the separation from the motherland are full of longing for his native land, longing, unwittingly bursting out of the depths of the heart of the national poet.

The homesickness is depicted unusually strongly in the famous poem "My people are", beginning with the words:

If you want to know about my people, Kozhban,
My people are wearing black hats, like a cauldron...
(Translated by E. Yemelyanov).

In this poem, the poet calls the disparate Karakalpak tribes and clans to national unity, dreams of them acting together for the sake of their happiness, in the name of their freedom.

In 1999, the 175th anniversary of the birth of the classic of Karakalpak poetry Azhiniyaz was widely celebrated throughout Uzbekistan. On December 18 of this year, festive celebrations dedicated to this significant event in the life of the republic were held in Nukus. To this national celebration of the great poet, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov sent a greeting, which reads: "The Karakalpak people have passed through the paths of the trials of the past with honor. The inner world, the subtle philosophy of the Karakalpaks were reflected in his oral work, in the legacy of such great poets as Berdakh, Kunkhoja. Poet Ajiniyaz, whose 175th anniversary we are celebrating today, is one of these unique figures. In his works, the dreams and aspirations of the people, their faith in a bright future, tender and loving attitude to life are conveyed at a high artistic level and masterfully."

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